

Reassessing “Bidirectional ventricular tachycardia due to hypokalemia”: A critical case review

Stone Johnson¹ & Sean Kay²

¹St. George's University School of Medicine

²Stony Brook University

Author Note

We have no known conflict of interest.

Corresponding author is Sean Kay. Email: sean.kay@stonybrook.edu

Abstract

Bidirectional ventricular tachycardia is a rare ventricular arrhythmia characterized by alternating QRS morphology on the electrocardiogram. We comment on and provide an alternative explanation for a reported case of hypokalemia-induced bidirectional ventricular tachycardia, a phenomenon rarely reported and studied in the literature. Analysis of the electrocardiogram during the tachycardic episode compared to the baseline electrocardiogram demonstrates significant similarities in mean electrical axis and QRS morphology, as well as a lack of clear atrioventricular dissociation. In considering the electrocardiographic features as well as the patient's clinical history, the rhythm is more consistent with sinus rhythm in the presence of an intraventricular conduction delay with ventricular bigeminy. This case highlights the importance of critically analyzing suspected bidirectional ventricular tachycardia and emphasizes the value of utilizing baseline electrocardiograms for comparison and diagnosis.

Keywords: Bidirectional ventricular tachycardia, electrocardiography, hypokalemia, ventricular bigeminy

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Introduction

We comment on a reported case of hypokalemia-induced bidirectional ventricular tachycardia by Santos et al. (2018). The case describes an 81-year-old woman presenting to the emergency department with hypokalemia following an episode of vomiting and diarrhea. The initial 12-lead electrocardiogram (ECG) that was obtained shows a non-narrow complex bidirectional tachycardia which was diagnosed as bidirectional ventricular tachycardia (figure 1). After conversion, a follow-up 12-lead ECG was performed which showed sinus rhythm (figure 2). It is our recommendation to reconsider this diagnosis in favor of sinus rhythm in the presence of an intraventricular conduction delay with ventricular bigeminy, given the morphology and mean electrical axis similarities between the 12-lead ECG performed during the tachycardic episode and the follow-up 12-lead ECG which demonstrated sinus rhythm, as well as due to the patient’s medical history—or lack thereof—predisposing them to bidirectional ventricular tachycardia.

Figure 1: ECG obtained during tachycardic episode (Santos et al., 2018)

Figure 2: Follow-up ECG showing sinus rhythm (Santos et al., 2018)

Evidence for Reconsideration

Hypokalemia is neither a well-known nor a well-accepted etiology of bidirectional ventricular tachycardia, a point acknowledged in the original case report by Santos et al. (2018). Bidirectional ventricular tachycardia has several known and studied causes, including myocardial ischemia or infarction, digoxin toxicity, catecholaminergic polymorphic ventricular tachycardia, and myocarditis. There was another previously documented case of hypokalemia-induced bidirectional ventricular tachycardia, which was reported in 1976 in a patient with familial hypokalemic periodic paralysis. While hypokalemia is not a well-known etiology of bidirectional ventricular tachycardia, it is a well-known etiology of ventricular bigeminy (Almarzuqi et al., 2022; Kyaw & Maung, 2022).

Even if hypokalemia-induced bidirectional ventricular tachycardia is regarded as a likely cause of this patient's ECG abnormalities, those abnormalities must be examined closely with the baseline 12-lead ECG. The 12-lead ECG showing sinus rhythm that was obtained following termination of the described episode of bidirectional ventricular tachycardia is consistent in morphology with the alternating QRS complexes with a normal mean electrical axis in the 12-lead ECG collected during the tachycardic episode (i.e., the predominantly positive complexes in leads I and II). In a different case report of a patient with bidirectional ventricular tachycardia, it is acknowledged that the QRS axis shifted 180 degrees, which cannot be as appreciated in this case of diagnosed bidirectional ventricular tachycardia (Sachdeva et al., 2020). In the 12-lead ECG obtained showing a non-narrow complex bidirectional tachycardia, it should be recognized that the QRS axis between alternating complexes is not completely oppositional as it should be in bidirectional ventricular tachycardia—this can be especially appreciated in lead V3 (figure 1). Further, the lack of alternating left- and right-axis deviation is less indicative of bidirectional ventricular tachycardia, a phenomenon explained by Richter & Brugada (2009).

Notably, it is also evident that the S wave amplitude for the identified alternating complexes in the tachycardic episode are also the same amplitude as the S waves in the follow-up 12-lead ECG, at approximately 6 millimeters in lead V1. The morphology holds consistent between the tachycardic episode and the follow-up, suggesting conduction through the same pathway during both the tachycardic episode and the follow-up. It can be expected that this patient has aberrant conduction which is slightly prolonging the QRS duration in the alternating complexes that we are describing as non-ventricular and likely of sinus origin in the tachycardic 12-lead ECG as well as in the follow-up 12-lead ECG. Nonetheless, the QRS duration in the described alternating complexes is not as prolonged as would be expected in bidirectional ventricular tachycardia.

One of the most distinguishing features of bidirectional ventricular tachycardia is the presence of atrioventricular (AV) dissociation. There is no apparent AV dissociation in the 12-lead ECG obtained during the tachycardic episode. While AV dissociation in the presence of a wide-complex tachycardia strongly supports the diagnosis of ventricular tachycardia, its absence does not necessarily omit the possibility of ventricular tachycardia. However, the lack of clear AV dissociation in this case does make a rhythm of ventricular origin substantially less likely (Richter & Brugada, 2009).

While there are not significant compensatory pauses present as would traditionally be expected in ventricular bigeminy, this is not necessarily indicative of bidirectional ventricular tachycardia. In a case report on ventricular bigeminy with interpolation, it was described that the sinus complexes had a prolonged PR interval as a result of the interpolation (Denes, 1981). However, there is not a substantial amount of literature on this topic with its relation to interpolated ventricular bigeminy mimicking bidirectional ventricular tachycardia. An alternative explanation for the tachycardic episode that may mimic bidirectional ventricular tachycardia is a rhythm of middle or inferior junctional origin. A phenomenon of ventricular bigeminy with interpolation would explain the lack of visible P waves seen in the initial 12-lead ECG, due to the prolonged PR interval that can occur with interpolation even in sinus rhythm with ventricular bigeminy.

Ventricular bigeminy is a well-studied phenomenon that can mimic bidirectional ventricular tachycardia as described by Ali et al. (2013). Further, alternating bundle branch blocks can also be a mimic of bidirectional ventricular tachycardia. It is worth noting that there is an intraventricular conduction delay present in the follow-up 12-lead ECG that was performed, which can be appreciated in leads V1-V3 (figure 2). This further increases suspicion for an alternative explanation to the diagnosis of bidirectional ventricular tachycardia. \

Discussion

This case demonstrates the difficulties of diagnosing bidirectional ventricular tachycardia, as it can often be mimicked by other electrophysiologic phenomena including ventricular bigeminy with aberrancy. Features such as QRS morphology, comparison to the follow-up electrocardiogram, other electrocardiographic findings, and patient history increases suspicion for an alternative explanation as opposed to bidirectional ventricular tachycardia. We respectfully dissent from the original diagnosis of hypokalemia-induced bidirectional ventricular tachycardia. Further case studies examining ways to distinguish bidirectional ventricular

tachycardia from electrophysiologic phenomena mimicking it should be explored in future literature on this topic.

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